

CANCERTOOL: a visualization and representation interface to exploit cancer datasets

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Availability: <http://web.bioinformatics.cicbiogune.es/CANCERTOOL/>

The codebase and databases are freely available upon request.

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36 *The authors declare no conflict of interest.*

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40 With the advent of OMICs technologies, both individual research groups and consortia have spear-
41 headed the characterization of human samples of multiple pathophysiological origins, resulting in
42 thousands of archived genomes and transcriptomes. Although a variety of web tools are now available
43 to extract information from OMICs data, their utility has been limited by the capacity of non-
44 bioinformatician researchers to exploit the information. To address this problem, we have developed
45 **CANCERTOOL**, a web-based interface that aims to overcome the major limitations of public
46 transcriptomics dataset analysis for highly prevalent types of cancer (breast, prostate, lung, and
47 colorectal). **CANCERTOOL** provides rapid and comprehensive visualization of gene expression data for
48 the gene(s) of interest in well-annotated cancer datasets. This visualization is accompanied by
49 generation of reports customized to the interest of the researcher (e.g., editable figures, detailed
50 statistical analyses, and access to raw data for reanalysis). It also carries out gene-to-gene correlations
51 in multiple datasets at the same time or using preset patient groups. Finally, this new tool solves the
52 time-consuming task of performing functional enrichment analysis with gene sets of interest using up to
53 11 different databases at the same time. Collectively, **CANCERTOOL** represents a simple and freely
54 accessible interface to interrogate well-annotated datasets and obtain publishable representations that
55 can contribute to refinement and guidance of cancer-related investigations at all levels of hypotheses
56 and design.

57
58 **Keywords:** Cancer, bioinformatics, genetic expression, integration, editable results

59

60 **Statement of significance:** In order to facilitate access of research groups without bioinformatics support to
61 public transcriptomics data, we have developed a free online tool with an easy-to-use interface that allows
62 researchers to obtain quality information in a readily publishable format.

63 Introduction

64 Cancer encompasses a large collection of diseases that extensively vary in terms of mutation load, driver
65 pathobiological programs, metabolic needs and microenvironmental constraints (1). This heterogeneity is largely
66 responsible for the current challenges we face in terms of patient classification and effective treatments (2). The
67 mutational backpack of tumors has been the main focus of research in recent years (3). However, current data
68 indicates that understanding of genome-wide transcriptional programs can also provide important information for
69 patient stratification, diagnosis and the determination of possible therapeutic protocols. In this context,
70 normalized procedures have been established to make transcriptomic data publicly available (4). However, the
71 utilization of these databases to extract information still represents an important limitation for research groups
72 that do not have adjacent bioinformatics support. To bypass this problem, various computational tools and
73 portals have been created. For example, the GEO database (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/>) (5) has been
74 developed by the NCBI to facilitate the public access to functional genomics data (including gene expression
75 data). The tools available in this database allow the simple visualization of data upon specific queries. However,
76 specialized personnel is still required to extract information on the cancer type of interest, export the data
77 obtained, perform clinical associations, or to obtain publication-grade representations from the data generated.
78 Some of the latter aspects are fulfilled by Oncomine (6), a commercial platform that offers several tools for
79 analyzing gene expression in multiple sets of data from independent studies at the same time. It also allows
80 searching information through various filters (such as the type of cancer, sample types, names of specific genes,
81 etc.) and returns results from multiple analyses carried out using gene information according to the requirements
82 set forth by the user. A main problem of this tool is that it requires a costly subscription in order to get access to
83 all its capabilities. It is also far from being user friendly for non-specialists. More recently, cBioportal has become
84 the most attractive portal for cancer OMICs analysis (7,8). This tool is free and enables the user to browse
85 through multiple datasets and query multiple genes. It also provides a user-friendly representation for data
86 interpretation. However, re-analyses from raw data are frequently required for publication-quality figures and the
87 browsing for information regarding gene expression alterations in cancer is still time consuming owing to the
88 multiple options and datasets available. Whereas non-bioinformatician cancer researchers could access all
89 required transcriptomics information for major cancer types with the aforementioned tools, the process still
90 requires considerable training, over dozens of clicks, and additional time for preparing publication-quality figures.

91 In this work, we report CANCERTOOL (<http://web.bioinformatics.cicbiogune.es/CANCERTOOL>), a new
92 portal that aims at solving the foregoing problems. This tool focuses on the four major tumor types (breast,

93 prostate, colorectal, lung) in its first version, although it is engineered to quickly incorporate new studies from
94 either the aforementioned tumors or other cancer types. Importantly, the datasets contained in CANCERTOOL
95 have been carefully curated to offer various types of clinical data-related to each cancer such as disease
96 progression, pathological, and molecular annotations. All these results are presented in a format that allows the
97 user to screen through tens of candidate genes within minutes as well as to perform customized analyses for
98 retrieval of high quality representations, detailed statistics, and access to raw data for reanalysis of the selected
99 hits. CANCERTOOL offers the opportunity of performing comparative gene expression analyses among
100 investigator-selected conditions (e.g., sample type, disease stage, pathological and molecular features) and to
101 estimate the association of candidate gene expression to disease progression. To provide a complete toolbox in
102 a stereotypic OMICs cancer research project, CANCERTOOL includes a functional enrichment package with
103 access to 11 databases that can be exploited with either in-house experimental- or CANCERTOOL-derived gene
104 sets. As such, CANCERTOOL aims at providing access to transcriptomics cancer data selected for rich clinical
105 annotation not currently offered by the tools discussed above. Ultimately, this tool focuses on free, rapid, and
106 comprehensive visualization analyses of transcriptomics results that is ready to use for cancer researchers that
107 lack bioinformatics support.

108 **Materials and Methods**

109 **Available datasets and its normalization**

110 For the development of CANCERTOOL, data from the public repository GEO (5), cBioportal (for METABRIC,
111 cbioportal.org) and, from the project TCGA (<https://cancergenome.nih.gov/>) (4) were obtained. Specifically, gene
112 expression and phenotypic data from patients with breast, colorectal, lung or prostate cancer were retrieved. The
113 data sets identification and related cancer information can be found in **Table 1** and in the Datasets section in
114 CANCERTOOL. In addition, the Datasets section also offers full access to all phenotypic information included in
115 every dataset for all patients. The raw gene expression data available in the repositories, in the form of
116 fluorescence intensity or number of sequencing reads, were first log₂ transformed and quartile normalized (9).

117 Data coming from the GEO repository were downloaded as series matrix, and were log₂ transformed and
118 quartile normalized when needed, METABRIC data were downloaded as log₂ transformed and normalized from
119 cBioPortal, while TCGA data were downloaded as upper quartile normalized RSEM count, which has been log₂
120 transformed. Regarding data donated by collaborators, they have been treated as mentioned on Vallejo *et al.*
121 (10).

122 **CANCERTOOL architecture**

123 mRNA and long intergenic non-coding RNA (LINC) expression levels and clinical data were indexed and queried
124 via MySQL relational database with a MyISAM engine, improving the speed for the retrieval of results.
125 CANCERTOOL is located on a Linux/Apache server to enable both enhanced stability and security. Its
126 architecture is built around a three-tier model: the presentation, the logic, and the database tiers. The
127 presentation tier, implemented in PHP/CSS and JavaScript, handles user's requests and displays data results.
128 The logic tier contains most of the functions to handle data transfer between the presentation and the database
129 tier, being implemented using Perl and R scripting languages. The database tier is where data are located and is
130 the responsible for accessing them.

131 **Statistical analysis**

132 CANCERTOOL includes various statistical calculations to compare the levels of expression of a gene among
133 different types of patients, to study the disease-free survival depending on the expression levels of target genes,
134 to make correlations between pairs of genes and to perform enrichment analysis of gene sets.

135 For the comparison of mRNA and/or LINC expression levels among different types of patient specimens,
136 normality was assessed and parametric tests were set to compare means among groups. CANCEERTOOL
137 performs Student T test to interrogate the differences between two groups. For comparisons among means of
138 more than two groups of specimens for a given gene, ANOVA test is performed. In custom studies a posthoc
139 analysis is included using Bonferroni and Tukey HSD (11,12). In addition, when data from more than two dataset
140 is produced in a given analysis, Edgington method is applied (The Sum of P values) (13) to ascertain whether
141 the integration of all datasets yield a significant difference. Also in custom analyses, p-values have been
142 adjusted using Benjamini–Hochberg method. In all the cases, a p-value ≤ 0.05 is considered as significant. All
143 the analyses were performed with R, using stats (14) package for adjusting and posthoc analyses, metap
144 (<https://rdr.io/cran/metap/>) package for the calculation of Edgington method and ggplot2 for the violin plots (15).
145 CANCEERTOOL provides to distinct statistical analyses for the Correlations section based on the criteria of the
146 end-user. Pearson and/or the Spearman correlation coefficient is calculated for every pair of genes, and the
147 statistical significance is provided. For correlations that generate results in more than two datasets, a
148 "Coherence" value is also calculated. This parameter informs the user about the consistent directional
149 correlation present in the analysis when integrating the results from all available datasets. An accountable
150 correlation is estimated when the p-value ≤ 0.05 , and the correlation coefficient is greater than 0.2 (for direct
151 correlations) or lower than -0.2 (inverse correlations). Analyses that present the accountable correlations with the
152 same directionality in more than 50% of the available datasets are flagged as "Coherent". In custom analyses, p-
153 values have been adjusted using FDR method. All the correlation analyses and graphs were performed with R
154 while correlation heatmaps were drawn using a custom version of the heatmap.2 function from package gplots
155 (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/gplots/index.html>).

156 For survival analyses, CANCEERTOOL performs a quartile-based separation of patients based on the
157 expression of the gene of interest. Next, the survival curves are represented using the Kaplan-Meier estimator as
158 quartile 1 (Q1, 25% of patient specimens with the lowest expression), quartile 4 (Q4, 25% of patient specimens
159 with the highest expression) and Q2+Q3 (the 50% of patient specimens with expression ranging between Q1
160 and Q4). The statistical significance is provided by the Mantel-Cox (also known as Logrank) test. This test was
161 selected because it assumes the randomness of the possible censorship (16). All the survival analyses and
162 graphs were performed with R (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/survival/citation.html>) and *P* values \leq
163 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

164 Gene enrichment analysis employs a hypergeometric test and FDR method to adjust p-values. This
165 methodology was chosen because data come from a simple random sampling without replacement. Please note
166 that whereas previous analyses are associated to datasets contained in CANTOOL, gene enrichment can
167 be performed using CANTOOL-derived information (obtained in the complementary tools) or with user-
168 defined gene sets. Gene Enrichment analysis can be performed in the databases indicated in **Supplementary**
169 **Table 1**. An adjusted p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant. All the calculations have been
170 performed with R.

171 **Results**

172 CANCEERTOOL is a freely accessible web tool which allows the user to query a database formed by manually
173 curated transcriptomics cancer datasets for the most prevalent tumor types. The tool is organized in three
174 different sections: Basic Analyses, Correlations and Gene Enrichment. It also allows the user to access the
175 Manual, Datasets, information related to the developers, and contact information in the Datasets (Help, About
176 Us, and Contact Us sections).

177 ***Basic Analyses***

178 This section has been designed to satisfy an important requirement for cancer researchers, namely browsing
179 rapidly through the results in the most prevalent tumor types. A summary PDF of the results is provided with the
180 aim of complying with a rapid *Go/No-Go* decision-making strategy. The current output of CANCEERTOOL is
181 compatible with the selection of best candidates in the tumor type of interest based on the mRNA and/or LINC
182 expression profile among dozens of queried genes in a matter of minutes. The end-user receives visual
183 representations related to: (i) Basic statistical analyses for the gene(s) of interest; (ii) comparisons of the relative
184 expression of the gene(s) under analysis in tumor versus healthy tissue, in different pathological features (e.g.
185 stage, Gleason score, location), molecular characteristics of the tumors (e.g. ER status, *KRAS* and *EGFR*
186 mutation status), molecular subtype (e.g. luminal, basal, HER2+ in the case of breast tumor samples), and
187 disease progression (i.e., primary tumor vs. metastasis, disease-free/metastasis-free/overall survival). The
188 mRNA and/or LINC expression comparisons among groups of specimens are provided as easily interpretable
189 violin plots that, in each case, provide additional information on sample size estimation. Another advantage is
190 that avoids the limitations usually observed when using other type of representations (e.g., dot plots) when the
191 datasets encompass large sample size (17). This representation is visually appealing and informative, and it is a
192 distinctive value when compared to other visualization tools (**Suppl. Fig. 1**). Survival analysis is provided using a
193 Kaplan-Meier estimator that divides the sample set according to the expression of the mRNA and/or LINC of
194 interest in quartiles. With this output, CANCEERTOOL facilitates rapid decision-making by the user without any
195 type of previous knowledge on bioinformatics. Furthermore, it also enables further analyses of the mRNA and/or
196 LINC(s) that comply with pre-established selection criteria according to the needs of the customer. In **Figure 1**,
197 we depict as illuminating example the analysis of a gene identified as potential regulator of prostate cancer
198 biology using this type of *Basic Analyses* tool. This gene was subsequently corroborated as an important player
199 in this tumor type (18). The Summary file provides rapid and visual information regarding the downregulation of

200 the *Microphthalmia-associated transcription factor (MITF)* in 3 out of 5 prostate cancer (PCa) datasets analyzed
201 (**Fig. 1A**). Furthermore, it shows that such a deregulation is associated with the progression of the disease
202 towards metastasis in 4 out of the 5 datasets analyzed using CANCEERTOOL (**Fig. 1B**). These analyses also make
203 apparent that the expression of this gene does not have any statistically significant correlation with the Gleason
204 score (**Fig. 1C**). It does predict disease-free survival of prostate cancer when patients are stratified according to
205 the first quartile (Q1) of *MITF* expression (**Fig. 1D**). However, a conclusive result would require further
206 customized analysis. Importantly, the user can obtain publication-quality images for each of the foregoing study
207 (see **Fig. 1**). It is also possible to conduct more detailed statistical analyses and representations stemming from
208 the raw data in the Custom section. Thus, together with the quartile-based analysis, this custom study allowed
209 us to obtain representations of two groups of *MITF* expression divided by the mean expression of this gene in
210 the cohort of interest (**Suppl. Fig. 2**). Additional personalized cut-offs can be established through the access to
211 raw data files provided in the custom analysis. Indeed, the inverse association of *MITF* to disease-free survival
212 was significant in two out of three datasets analyzed when the patients within the first quartile of gene expression
213 were compared to the rest of the cohort (18). Of note, in support of the possibility of monitoring the expression of
214 LINC_s in CANCEERTOOL, **Suppl. Fig. 3** depicts the expression of LINC00116 in a dataset per tumor type.

215 **Correlations**

216 CANCEERTOOL can calculate and plot gene-to-gene correlations in the annotated tumor types and datasets. The
217 output of this tool has been designed for rapid *Go/No-Go* decisions. The tool allows up to 5 (list 1) x 10 (list 2)
218 gene comparison. From the summary analysis, the user obtains two types of output files: (i) a PDF with the
219 correlation results visualized as a heatmap representation per gene (from list 1) that is subject to correlations
220 against a gene set (list 2), in which significant correlations (that reach a criteria of $p \leq 0.05$ and $-0.2 \geq R \geq 0.2$)
221 are indicated with an asterisk (**Fig. 2**); (ii) a PDF depicting, for each gene-to-gene correlation, the study in
222 various patient subgroups (e.g. non-tumoral tissue, cancer specimens, cancer subtypes, progression stages)
223 (**Suppl. Fig. 4**). The correlation analyses can be also customized in order to select either the datasets or the
224 patient subsets where to perform the correlations and the type of statistics (Pearson and/or Spearman). The
225 results are finally presented in several outputs, including high-resolution figures, raw data for reanalysis, and
226 tables including the calculated correlation coefficients and p-values (and Benjamini–Hochberg correction) for
227 each of the primary datasets utilized by the tool. The table also includes a “coherence” calculation that estimates
228 the robustness of gene-to-gene association across all the datasets that have been interrogated. *Coherence*
229 estimates consistent correlations when more than 50% of the datasets show a significant and unidirectional

230 correlation with correlation coefficient greater than 0.2 (for direct correlations) or lower than -0.2 (for inverse
231 correlations) (**Suppl. Table 2**). The *Correlations* section in CANCEERTOOL can aid the researcher in the
232 screening and selection of the best potential gene associations to uncover functional implications in cancer (18).

233 **Gene Enrichment**

234 Cancer research studies often exploit OMICs-derived data to decipher the molecular mechanisms associated
235 with changes in the expression of either a gene or pathway of interest. The result of such analysis usually
236 includes large lists of perturbed genes, transcripts and/or proteins. Whereas gene-by-gene annotation can be
237 useful to define individual candidate genes at the core of a given molecular mechanism, bioinformatics also
238 offers the possibility of using more integrative analyses from gene lists to unveil pathways and/or regulatory hubs
239 that would otherwise remain hidden. There are several databases that perform complementary enrichments.
240 However, they usually require complex and lengthy analytical steps that are not usually easily to implement by
241 non-specialists. To tackle this customer demand, CANCEERTOOL includes an *Additional Analyses* section where
242 we offer researchers a simplified and comprehensive access to additional aspects related to gene regulation and
243 functional integration. These tools enable the researcher to round up OMICs-related cancer studies and,
244 following the overall philosophy of all the tools associated with this platform, generate output data in publication
245 quality images and with the potential of subsequent customer-driven re-analyses. To this end, CANCEERTOOL
246 harbors 11 independent enrichment databases, including the basic Gene Ontology analysis (GO, biological
247 process (GOBP), molecular function (GOMF) and cell compartment (GOCC)), pathways and pathophysiological
248 processes (KEGG, Biocarta, Reactome, Biocarta, Onco, DOSE, HIPC, Connectivity Map), and the upstream
249 regulatory cue prediction tool (TFT, MIR). Results are presented as a platform-generated spreadsheet per
250 enrichment database that highlights type of main enriched functions, the prevalence of such functions within the
251 gene list, and statistical significance of the associations sieved according to the Benjamini–Hochberg correction
252 (adjusted p-value). The output spreadsheets are further complemented with a visual representation that depicts
253 the 10 most significant functions per database sorted according to adjusted p-value (**Fig. 3**).

254

255 Discussion

256 The exploitation of data from publicly available datasets has become the bottleneck for researchers that do not
257 have a strong bioinformatics background or facilities. Various tools do offer data browsing and analysis.
258 However, the interpretation, and representation of these data is still complex and cumbersome (see
259 Introduction). This issue is particularly important in the context of cancer research, where the availability of data
260 is overwhelming and grows exponentially every year. In this context, the bioinformatics capability of a lab is a
261 differentiating factor to increase the efficacy, the productivity and the biomedical impact of the results. Public
262 dataset exploitation can be instrumental for the refinement of hypotheses, the selection of candidate genes (thus
263 reducing the time and cost of exploratory experiments) and the validation of mechanistic studies.

264 CANCEERTOOL has been specifically designed to fulfill this need in cancer research and to complement the
265 capabilities of other existing tools and portals. Its main features include: (i) the ability to provide to users a rapid
266 evaluation of gene expression data for the queried gene(s); (ii) ensuring full availability of the raw data used in
267 the analyses; (iii) providing high-quality, and further editable, figures and (iv) making possible functional
268 annotations various tools to facilitate the association of the gene(s) of interest with specific functional networks,
269 hubs, and pathophysiological programs (**Fig. 4**). These features are given in an easy-to-use platform that will
270 enable cancer researchers to go from a candidate gene list to the final publication-grade representation of their
271 best candidates in a short time frame. Furthermore, its ability to provide basic gene expression comparisons
272 among patient subgroups and correlations among genes of interest in various datasets enables cancer
273 researchers to maximize the invested time and effort, and in turn to make significant advances in the postulated
274 research question. CANCEERTOOL includes clinical and molecular features based on the availability of the
275 datasets of origin. Thus, as more clinical data-rich studies are produced, the parameters of analysis included in
276 this tool will progressively increase.

277 This tool has been built using public transcriptomics datasets from four major tumor types. This strategy
278 stems from the importance of carefully selecting and curating datasets that are rich in clinical, pathological and
279 molecular data associated with each sample. We have prioritized the inclusion of a selected number of datasets
280 to ensure that the interpretation of the results is rapid and efficient without compromising the robustness or
281 translational potential of the results. However, CANCEERTOOL has been designed to allow its subsequent
282 expansion according to the needs of cancer researchers. Hence, the pipeline for dataset inclusion in
283 CANCEERTOOL is ready to progressively incorporate additional datasets and cancer types. Further

284 improvements can be done at the level of the statistics used and the type of graphical outputs to enrich the
285 summary and custom analyses, always keeping in mind that they must be generated in quick and easy manner
286 (the *Go/No-Go* strategy) to be understood and evaluated. Moreover, the support for gene signatures (average
287 signal of various genes within a functional group) in the sections *Basic Analyses* and *correlations* will expand the
288 use of the interface. A similar strategy to the transcriptomics analysis presented herein can be applied to other
289 OMICs layers. As an example, the inclusion of methylation studies could be an invaluable improvement for
290 users, if it were to be integrated with the transcriptomics studies. However, to date there are still few datasets in
291 which data from the methylome and transcriptome for the same specimens are available. The *Additional*
292 *Analyses* section can be also expanded to include additional tools that can aid the researcher to gather valuable
293 information about a gene(s) of interest. Potential tools of interest include Touchstone (<https://clue.io/touchstone>)
294 and DEPMAP (<https://depmap.org/portal/>) (19).

295 Our capacity to accrue empirical data is no longer the bottleneck in cancer research. With the appropriate
296 bioinformatics expertise and access to public OMICs datasets, a hypothesis can be tested, refined and the
297 molecular mechanism of candidate genes can be predicted *in silico*. This strategy rises considerably the success
298 rate and biomedical impact of cancer research projects. CANCERTOOL brings unique visualization and
299 representation capabilities to cancer research teams that lack the personnel or the expertise to perform
300 bioinformatics analyses, thus complementing and enriching the repertoire of available web tools.

301 **Acknowledgements**

302 Apologies to those whose related publications were not cited due to space limitations. We are grateful to Iñaki
303 Lazaro for the design of the tumor type logos, Evarist Planet and Antoni Berenguer for insightful discussions and
304 the Carracedo lab for valuable input. V.T. is funded by Fundación Vasca de Innovación e Investigación
305 Sanitarias, BIOEF (BIO15/CA/052), the AECC J.P. Bizkaia and the Basque Department of Health (2016111109).
306 The work of A. Carracedo is supported by the Basque Department of Industry, Tourism and Trade (Etortek) and
307 the department of education (IKERTALDE IT1106-16, also participated by A. Gomez-Muñoz), the BBVA
308 foundation, the MINECO (SAF2016-79381-R (FEDER/EU); Severo Ochoa Excellence Accreditation SEV-2016-
309 0644; Excellence Networks SAF2016-81975-REDT), European Training Networks Project (H2020-MSCA-ITN-
310 308 2016 721532), the AECC IDEAS16 (IDEAS175CARR) and the European Research Council (Starting Grant
311 336343, PoC 754627). CIBERONC was co-funded with FEDER funds. The work of A. Aransay is supported by
312 the Basque Department of Industry, Tourism and Trade (Etortek and Elkartek Programs), the Innovation
313 Technology Department of Bizkaia County, CIBERehd Network and Spanish MINECO the Severo Ochoa
314 Excellence Accreditation (SEV-2016-0644). I.A. is funded by a Basque Government predoctoral grant
315 (PRE_2017_2_0028). X.R.B. is supported by grants from the Castilla-León Government (BIO/SA01/15,
316 CSI049U16), Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO) (SAF2015-64556-R), Worldwide
317 Cancer Research (14-1248), Ramón Areces Foundation and the Spanish Society against Cancer
318 (GC16173472GARC). Funding from MINECO to X.R.B. is partially contributed by the European Regional
319 Development Fund. The work of FJP is supported by the MINECO (BIO2016-77998-R) and ELKARTEK
320 Programme of the Basque Government (KK-2016/00026).

321 **Authors' contributions**

322 ARC designed and developed the tool, obtained and curated the data, unless specified otherwise. VT and NM-M
323 contributed to the definition of the aims and output of the tool, as well as testing and detecting bugs during its
324 development. AC-M, LC and IH and contributed to the alfa-testing of the tool. RRG provided dataset suggestions
325 and helped in the identification of relevant outputs of the tool. SV and EG provided dataset suggestions and
326 helped beta-testing the tool. FP and IA provided statistical support and beta-tested the tool. VQ, LFL-M, RF-C
327 and XRB performed beta-testing of the tool. JT co-supervised the work of IH. AG-M co-supervised the work of
328 LC. AC and AMA directed the project, conceived the development of the tool, supervised its production and
329 wrote the manuscript.

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- 427

428 **Table 1.** All the available cancer types and datasets considered in CANTERTOOL.

Breast cancer	Colorrectal cancer	Lung adenocarcinoma	Prostate cancer
Ivshina <i>et al.</i> (20)	Colonomics https://www.colonomics.org/	Chitale <i>et al.</i> (21)	Glinksy <i>et al.</i> (22)
Lu <i>et al.</i> (23)	Jorissen <i>et al.</i> (24)	Okayama <i>et al.</i> (25)	Grasso <i>et al.</i> (26)
METABRIC (27)	Kemper <i>et al.</i> (28)	Shedden <i>et al.</i> (29)	Lapointe <i>et al.</i> (30)
Pawitan <i>et al.</i> (31)	Laibe <i>et al.</i> (32)	TCGA (RNA seq) https://cancergenome.nih.gov/	Taylor <i>et al.</i> (33)
TCGA (microarray) https://cancergenome.nih.gov/	Marisa <i>et al.</i> (34)	Wilkerson <i>et al.</i> (35)	TCGA (RNA seq) https://cancergenome.nih.gov/
Wang <i>et al.</i> (36)	Roepman <i>et al.</i> (37)		Tomlins <i>et al.</i> (38)
	TCGA (RNA seq) https://cancergenome.nih.gov/		Varambally <i>et al.</i> (39)

429

430 **Figure legends**

431 **Figure 1. A representative Summary output of the Basic Analysis section in CANCEERTOOL for the gene**
432 ***MITF* in prostate cancer datasets. A-C**, Violin plots depicting the expression of the gene of interest between
433 non-tumoral (Normal) and prostate cancer specimens (PCa) (A), among non-tumoral (Normal), primary tumor
434 and metastatic (PCa) specimens (B), and among PCa specimens of the indicated Gleason grade (GS: Gleason
435 score) (C) in the indicated datasets. The Y-axis represents the Log₂-normalized gene expression. **D**, Kaplan-
436 Meier curves representing the disease-free survival (DFS) of patient groups selected according to the quartile
437 expression of the gene of interest. Statistical analysis: Student's T-Test (A), ANOVA (B, C) and Mantel-Cox test
438 (D).

439 **Figure 2. Representative heatmap provided by CANCEERTOOL for the correlation analyses of *MITF***
440 **against the indicated genes in multiple prostate cancer datasets.** The color code indicates the correlation
441 status between the indicated gene pairs, being red towards 1 and blue towards -1. In case of NA, the cell is
442 colored in grey and with no data. Correlations are indicated with asterisks when they comply with the following
443 significance criteria: $p \leq 0.05$ and correlation coefficient greater than 0.2 for direct and lower than -0.2 for inverse
444 correlations. On the left side, the coherence among datasets is shown for each pair of genes (directional
445 correlation in more than 50% of datasets, being $p \leq 0.05$ and correlation coefficient greater than 0.2 for direct and
446 lower than -0.2 for inverse correlations). NA: not applicable. p: p-value.

447 **Figure 3. Example of the output figure provided by the Gene Enrichment analysis.** The results show a
448 histogram from the Molecular Function database within Gene Ontology. The ten terms with the highest
449 significance in adjusted FDR p-value, ordered by this field are included. The X-axis indicates the $-\text{Log}_{10}(\text{adjusted}$
450 $\text{p-value})$. The Y-axis includes information relative to the category, the Ratio and the adjusted p-value.

451 **Figure 4. Example of a workflow integrating CANCEERTOOL with empirical studies in cancer research.**
452 **1/1'**, initial selection of genes to be queried in CANCEERTOOL. Genes can be studied in a single cancer type (to
453 be selected in the interface) if it is predetermined (Step 1), or sequential analysis can be performed to gather
454 information about all cancer types available (Step 1'). The results will aid the user in the identification of the best
455 candidate genes for further analysis and the most promising cancer type where the research question is to be
456 developed. **2**, the selection of candidate genes can be followed by experimental approaches to shed light on the
457 mechanism of action, often accompanied with OMICs strategies to provide a comprehensive view of the
458 molecular alterations associated to the candidate gene(s). **3**, Once the researcher reaches the identification of

459 potential effectors, upstream regulators or gene lists perturbed upon manipulation of our gene(s) of interest,
460 CANCERTOOL can aid in the identification of most interesting candidates (based on gene expression alterations
461 in cancer patients, correlations analyses with the gene(s) driving the research project or enrichment analysis) to
462 identify molecular/pathological process and common regulatory cues predominant in the queried gene list. **4,**
463 these analyses can enable the user to further refine the mechanistic hypotheses and to reach relevant
464 conclusions.

A. Status in prostate cancer

B. Status by Progression

C. Status by Gleason Grade

D. Disease-Free Survival

MITF (Pearson correlation)

For datasets that contain insufficient number of samples to correctly perform the analysis, the requested correlation will be annotated as NA (Non Applicable)

